

Synthesis, Characterisation and Biological Screening of Nickel-containing Copolymer Films

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Nickel-containing copolymer films have been synthesised by copolymerisation of methyl methacrylate with styrene containing different concentration of polynickel acrylate initiated by benzoyl peroxide, and characterised by ir and nmr spectroscopy. Other properties such as chemical resistance, molecular weight, conductivity, adsorbity, softening range and biological screening, have been studied.

Metal-containing polymers have found extensive applications¹. Phosphorus-containing polymers are in general flame retardant². Platinum-containing polymers have been used in the treatment of tumours³ and germanium-containing polymers in the treatment of fibrosis of lungs⁴. However, a few reports are available on the synthesis of copolymer films⁵. The applications of metal-containing polymer films have not yet been fully investigated⁶. Therefore, we have undertaken a systematic study of nickel-containing copolymer films which is described herein.

Results and Discussion

The copolymer films are white, translucent, brittle, non-conducting and impermeable in water. The average molecular weight of copolymer films was found to increase sharply with increasing polynickel content. The softening range of metal-containing copolymer films was found in the range 88–145° (Table 1). The films are soluble at 30° and 80° in H₂SO₄, DMF, dichloroethane, ethyl acetoacetate, ethyl malonate, ethyl acetate, CCl₄, CHCl₃, dioxane, benzene and toluene, partially soluble in acetic anhydride, and insoluble in HNO₃, HCl, water, NaOH (0.1 N), DMSO and AcOH. Also at 30° the films are soluble in acetone, partially soluble in diethyl ether and insoluble in methanol, ethanol and petroleum ether. The adsorption of methanol is highest in a very short time while dimethyl sul-

phoxide and nitric acid also exhibit high adsorption but the adsorption of acetic acid being relatively low (Fig. 1).

The copolymer films show good bactericidal and fungicidal activities (Table 2). Antifungal activity of the films is not good as compared to bacterial species.

The ir spectrum of copolymer film of MMA with STY containing polynickel acrylate shows bands at 3 050, 3 010 and 2 920 cm⁻¹ with slight shifting from fundamental vibrations of the ester methyl group. The sharp bands at 1 710 and 1 600 cm⁻¹ could be assigned to carbonyl group and aromatic C–H stretch respectively. The C–H deformation bands appear at 1 525, 1 420 and 1 380 cm⁻¹ with slight shifting. The nmr spectrum of the copolymer film shows peaks at τ 2.1–2.6 (phenyl protons), 8.2–9.2 (methylene and methine protons) and 5.9–7.8 (methoxy protons of ester group).

Experimental

Methyl methacrylate (MMA) and styrene (STY) were washed with 4% NaOH to remove the stabiliser, then washed with water and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂. Nickel acrylate was prepared by the reported method⁷. Polynickel acrylate was prepared by using azobisisobutyronitrile as initiator at 80° using methanol as an inert solvent. Copolymer of MMA and STY was prepared at 80° using benzoyl peroxide (BPO) as an initiator using different concentra-

TABLE I—COMPOSITION OF REACTANT USED IN THE PREPARATION OF NICKEL-CONTAINING COPOLYMER FILMS

Film code	Components			Poly nickel acrylate mg	Poly-dispersity	MW GPC	Softening range °C
	BPO mol dm ⁻³ × 10 ⁻²	MMA mol dm ⁻³	STY mol dm ⁻³				
PF ₁	3.89	3.88	5.11	—	—	—	108–124
PF ₂	3.89	3.88	5.11	50	3.82	108494	14–145
PF ₃	4.12	5.49	3.57	50	—	—	88–100
PF ₄	3.40	6.92	2.25	50	—	—	110–115
PF ₅	3.89	3.88	5.11	25	3.15	96332	130–135
PF ₆	3.89	3.88	5.11	100	4.34	118963	126–134

Fig. 1. Plots of amount of solvents adsorbed vs time for polymer film.

tions of MMA. The polymerisation was performed for 5 h then copolymer was precipitated with acidified methanol.

TABLE 2—BIOLOGICAL SCREENING OF NICKEL-CONTAINING COPOLYMER FILMS AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS (ppm)

Film code	<i>E. coli</i>		<i>B. subt.</i>		<i>C. alb.</i>		
	500	1000	500	1000	250	500	1000
PF ₁	1.5	4.0	2.0	3.5	—	0.5	1.0
PF ₅	2.5	5.0	4.5	7.5	0.5	2.0	3.0
PF ₆	4.5	8.5	6.0	9.5	1.0	3.0	4.5

Preparation of film : Films were formed by dissolving copolymers of methyl methacrylate and styrene in benzene using a fixed concentration (15% by weight) of the solute. The solution was continuously stirred for about 40 min using magnetic stirrer to ensure homogenous mixing. For preparing metal-containing polymer films, different concentrations of polynickel acrylate were added. Films were cast on glass plate.

Gel permeation chromatogram was obtained using a

S.P.U. chromatograph using styrogel column (10^3 and 10^6 Å). Toluene was used as eluent at a flow rate of 1.0 g ml^{-1} . The concentration of the sample was 1.0 g ml^{-1} . A universal calibration curve was obtained using low molecular weight polystyrene standards.

In order to investigate the water permeability of the film, the end of a test tube containing saturated sugar solution was closed with the film. The test tube was then placed in a solution of potassium permanganate and this system was left for two days. The conductivity of copolymer film was checked by a Toshniwal CL 01.07A instrument using acetone as reference solvent.

To determine the solubility and chemical resistance, the film strip (~25 mg) was immersed in various organic and inorganic solvents at room temperature and at 60° , and the change in weight was noted. In order to study the phenomenon of adsorption, film strip (~25 mg) was immersed in various liquids (methanol, acetic acid, DMSO, nitric acid and sodium hydroxide) at 60° and after a relatively short time the increase in weight due to adsorption was noted.

Biological screening : The nickel-containing polymer alloys were screened for their fungicidal activity by agar plate technique and bactericidal activity by agar diffusion technique at concentrations 250, 500 and 1000 ppm in acetone (number of replication in each case was three) using *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Candida albicans*.

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